

ANALYSIS OF ALTERNATIVE MATERIALS FROM BANANA SHEATHS FOR FOOD PACKAGING CONTAINERS

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Abstract

The study of banana fibers aimed to study the fibers obtained from the fiber extraction process for use in food packaging. The research selected 8-9-month-old Nam Wa bananas with trunks 2-3 meters high, cut the banana trees about 20 centimeters, passed through the process of releasing steam followed by chemical treatment to extract banana fibers, carried out at boiling temperature for 60 minutes, then washed with clean water, and then pressed the banana fibers to remove excess water. The test weighed the banana fibers. After that, the banana samples packed in containers with open lids were put into an oven at 70 °C for 24 hours. From the statistics, it shows that all data sets follow a normal distribution. This type of graph is also a good way to consider whether the residuals from the regression analysis are normally distributed or not. The p-value for the test is 0.719, indicating that the data follow a normal distribution. From the Analysis of Variance, the P-Value is equal to 0.000, indicating that the pseudo stem banana from 12 layers of Namwa banana tree had no difference at the significance level of 0.000. The research selected 5 consecutive banana layers for research, and layers 3-7 were selected for further analysis. The results of the research found that banana fiber produced by the extraction of the exposed layers was a new and efficient production process, which produced the extracted layer through all layers. The 7 layer fiber had an average diameter of 125.7 μm, the highest, while the smallest fiber was layer 4, with an average diameter of 86.2 μm. It showed that the banana layer level affected the fiber size as the size increased with the layer, but there was no significant difference at the significance level of 0.000. It showed that the experimental results could be practically applied. From all 5 tested layers, all layers can be used as food packaging regardless of the banana layer level. Analysis of banana fiber layers produced by fiber extraction, the layer with large fibers also had a high swelling rate. The mixture of layer ratio 7 had a swelling rate of 3.88%, which would increase with the size of each layer of fiber.

Keywords: Alternative, Banana Fiber, Food Packaging.

1. INTRODUCTION

Banana plants are abundant in various tropical regions and have a brief harvest period. Utilizing parts of the banana plant that would otherwise be discarded as refuse promotes sustainability. Banana fiber

is a lingo-cellulosic fiber extracted from the pseudo-stem of banana plants. Banana fiber production offers economic opportunities, particularly in developing nations with prevalent banana plants. It can contribute to the creation of local jobs and the generation of local income. Thailand's banana industry has long been a pillar of the nation's agricultural sector. However, sustainable use of the banana plant has gained attention as artisans and entrepreneurs explore methods to utilize the wasteful pseudo-stems. Not only does this add value to the agricultural supply chain, but it also correlates with global trends in environmentally responsible practices.

Banana fibre extraction can be done through both manual and mechanical processes. Mechanical extraction is preferred over manual extraction due to its efficiency. Surface treatments are used to modify the fiber's surface for specific applications. In Thailand, a banana fiber extraction machine was designed and manufactured for small to medium-scale production of handicrafts. Chemical treatment, such as alkaline treatment, can improve the tensile strength of banana fiber and make it suitable for composite development [1]. Banana fiber can be used as a reinforcement material in polymer composites, resulting in improved mechanical properties [2]. Additionally, banana stem scutcher (BSS) waste can be used as an adsorbent for the removal of heavy metal ions from water. BSS has a high adsorption capacity for lead ions and can be recycled multiple times without significant loss in performance.

There is a concerted effort to improve the quality of banana fiber to satisfy the needs of various applications. Research focuses on refining the fiber's strength, flexibility, and texture through genetic modification, selective breeding, and improved cultivation practices. These improvements contribute to the fiber's versatility and usability in various industries. Anafack et al. [3] studied the effects of different extraction methods, consisting of water retting, dew retting, and rolling, on the physical and mechanical properties of William banana peduncle fibers. The physical and mechanical properties of the extracted fibers have been analyzed. Water retting was found to have a high yield compared to mechanical extraction. Enzymatic retting produced banana cellulose fibers with physical properties comparable to cotton fiber [4]. Banana pseudostem fiber, due to its high cellulose content and other properties, is used in various applications such as nano and microcrystalline cellulose, activated carbon, green composites, and technical textiles [5]. Chi et al. [6] discusses the design and manufacture of a banana fiber extraction machine for small and medium-scale handicraft production. It mentions that the machine was tested under different motor speeds and achieved extraction rates of 10.1%, 11.2%, and 10.8% at different speeds.

According to the investigation of the aforementioned inquiry, the quantity of banana fiber present in every individual stratum of banana bracts varies. Opting for a stratum boasting a substantial fiber content will inevitably impact the competitiveness of the merchandise.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Banana pseudo-stem from plants of the banana species Namwa Banana, aged between 8 and 9 months, with trunks measuring 2 to 3 meters in height. Cut the banana tree by measuring about 20 centimeters from the base of the tree. Discard the incomplete outermost layer of banana bracts. Each layer of banana bracts is cut to a size of 90 centimeters long and 5 centimeters wide, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1: Banana bracts layer

The recorded weight subsequent to this process was designated as the post-oven sample weight. Three replicates were conducted, and the data details are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Weight of banana bracts layer

Banana Bracts Layer	Weight (g)		
	T1	T2	T3
1	9.40	9.23	9.95
2	6.96	7.36	9.52
3	9.12	9.99	11.01
4	11.10	6.21	7.58
5	8.00	6.32	9.63
6	5.02	8.75	10.33
7	7.75	5.83	13.54
8	10.53	7.38	9.93
9	7.35	6.00	10.88
10	5.22	4.81	9.20
11	10.75	3.40	6.43
12	6.35	3.40	7.33

2.2 Banana fiber extraction

This study employs the method of Steam release followed by chemical treatment (SCM) in order to extract banana fiber. Due to the acidic nature of the binding materials cellulose (55–65%), hemicellulose (15–25%), lignin (10–15%), and pectin (3–5%)[5], degumming is typically accomplished using sodium carbonate, with the procedure conducted at boiling temperature for 60 minutes [7], as shown in Figure 2.

Fig 2: Banana pseudo-stem boiler

Following the boiling process, it is imperative to conduct a thorough rinsing of the water. Subsequently, the banana fibers should undergo a pressing procedure to extract excess water, followed by the determination of their weight. Following this, the specimen within the open-lidded container was placed in the oven, maintained at a temperature of 70°C, for a duration of 24 hours, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig 3: boiling process

Table 2: Weight of banana boiling process

Banana Bracts Layer	Weight (g)		
	T1	T2	T3
1	1.93	1.78	2.19
2	2.20	1.97	2.18
3	2.22	2.11	2.19
4	2.49	2.98	2.43
5	2.51	2.76	2.49
6	2.45	2.57	2.43
7	2.10	1.73	2.30
8	2.32	2.18	2.15
9	1.56	1.75	1.56
10	1.46	1.49	1.87
11	1.42	1.07	1.25
12	1.39	0.97	1.30

2.3 Statistical analysis

The data were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the determination of significant differences in the treatments. Least significance difference (LSD) tests were used to compare differences between treatments at 95% confidence level.

2.4 Morphology

by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, EM30P-AX, COXEM(KR)) at the voltage of 15 kV with magnification power 200X to 1000X Fiber Diameters and swelling after it has been coated with gold (Gold (Au), SPT-20, COXEM(KR)) [8]. The fiber's thicknesses were also measured for at least 5 values and then calculated for the average thickness.

2.5 Swelling ratio

The scaffold was put into the swelling test in order to find the difference of dry weight and wet weight of the scaffold in percentage. The dried scaffold was weighted and then soaked the scaffold under PBS buffer solution at the pH of 7.4 and temperature of 37 oC for 3 hours. Then both sides of the scaffold were wiped with low lint paper 10 seconds for each side and then weighted immediately.

The dry weight and wet weight were then calculated into percentage using the following formula as shown in (1). We then compared the resulted of swelling ratio of scaffolds from electrospinning technique.

$$\text{Swelling ratio} = \frac{W_{so} - W_o}{W_o} \quad (1)$$

Where as

W_{so} is the weight of scaffold after its water content was absorbed

W_o is the initial weight of the scaffold

Fig 4: Flow process chart

3. RESULTS

3.1 Probability Plot of Residuals

Residuals are estimates of experimental error obtained by subtracting the observed responses from the predicted responses.

Fig 5: Probability plot of residuals

From Figure 5, these normal probability plots show that all the datasets follow the normal distribution. This type of graph is also a great way to determine whether residuals from regression analysis are normally distributed. The p-value for the test is 0.719, which indicates that the data follow the normal distribution by Banana fiber extraction.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Sheet No	11	8.4854	0.77140	21.49	0.000
Error	24	0.8616	0.03590		
Total	35	9.347			

From table 3 From the Analysis of Variance table, the P-Value is 0.000, indicating that the 12-layer bananas are not different at the significance level of 0.000.

Table 4: Weight of banana boiling process

Banana Bracts Layer	Weight (g)		
	Before	After	Percentage reduction
1	9.53	1.97	79.35
2	7.94	2.12	73.37
3	10.04	2.17	78.35
4	8.30	2.63	68.26
5	7.98	2.59	67.58
6	8.03	2.48	69.12
7	9.04	2.04	77.40
8	9.28	2.22	76.13
9	8.08	1.62	79.90
10	6.41	1.61	74.97
11	6.86	1.25	81.77
12	5.69	1.22	78.60

From Table 4, five consecutive banana layers were selected for research. Layers 3-7 were selected for further analysis in the experiment.

Table 5: Condition banana layers

Banana Bracts Layer	Code
3	BL3
4	BL4
5	BL5
6	BL6
7	BL7

Condition banana layer3 code BL3 layer4 code BL4 layer5 code BL5 layer6 code BL6 and layer7 code BL7 shown in Table 5.

3.2 Surface morphology fiber

Morphology by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, EM30P-AX, COXEM(KR)) at the voltage of 11-15 kV with magnification power 200x after it has been coated with gold (Gold (Au), SPT-20, COXEM(KR)). The fiber's thicknesses were also measured for at least 5 values and then calculated for the average thickness.

Fig 6: SEM images of banana fiber

SEM images of banana fiber layer3 code BL3(A), layer4 code BL4(B), layer5 code BL5(C) layer6 code BL6(D) and layer7 code BL7(E) shown in Fig. 6.

Table 6: Diameter banana fiber

Code	Range of diameter (μm)	Average diameter (μm)
BL3	81.3-118.9	100.1
BL4	70.5-101.8	86.2
BL5	80.7-98.9	89.8
BL6	106.4-113.7	110.1
BL7	110.6-140.7	125.7

Table 6 revealed that when banana fiber layer 3-7, fiber’s size was decreased from 70.5 μm to 140.7 μm. SEM images of banana fiber with BL3 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 81.3 μm to 118.9 μm Average diameter 100.1 μm, BL4 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 70.5 μm to 101.8 μm Average diameter 86.2 μm, BL5 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 80.7 μm to 98.9 μm Average diameter 89.8 μm, BL6 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 106.4 μm to 113.7 μm Average diameter 110.1 μm, BL7 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 110.6 μm to 140.7 μm Average diameter 125.7 μm,

Fig 7: Show Graph of the result banana fiber slope from molding

Fig. 7. BL7 Average diameter 125.7 μm it has the highest slope. BL7 Average diameter 110.1 μm, BL6 Average diameter 100.1 μm, BL5 Average diameter 89.8 μm BL4 Average diameter 86.2 μm respectively.

Table 7: The swelling ratio of banana fiber

layer	Code	%				
3	BL3	3.19	3.12	3.61	3.60	3.38
4	BL4	3.10	3.41	3.62	3.52	2.90
5	BL5	4.23	3.90	3.65	3.87	3.72
6	BL6	3.31	2.84	3.23	3.38	5.50
7	BL7	4.26	3.21	4.41	4.35	3.17

Table 7 Swelling ratio to extract banana fiber were also measured for at 5 values and then calculated for the average. The dry weight and wet weight calculated into percentage using formula as shown in (1) swelling ratio of banana fiber.

Fig 8: Swelling ratio of banana fiber

Revealed that of banana fiber with the BL7 had swelling ratio of 3.88 % which was the highest. All banana fiber had average lower in swelling ratio compared with the layer, except for the case of banana fiber layer BL5 which was 3.87%, BL6 which was 3.65 %, BL3 which was 3.38 % and BL4 which was 3.31%

4. CONCLUSION

Banana fiber produced by extraction the layer revealed is a novel and efficient fabrication process that produced extraction the layer through the action of an external layer field to fiber total of 7 layer. BL7 Average diameter 125.7 μm it has the highest slope. BL4 Average diameter 86.2 μm respectively. It shows that the banana layer level affects the fiber size with increasing size according to the layer but there is no significant difference at the 0.000 level of significance. This shows that the results of the experiment can be applied practically from all 5 layers tested. It shows that all layers can be used as packaging regardless of the banana layer level.

Analyzing the banana fiber layer produced by fiber extraction the layer had fiber with large fiber size would also has high swelling ratio. Mixture of BL7 ratio had swelling ratio of 3.88%. When adding more layer, there will be more fiber as well, so the layer can be remembered.

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